

Application of electrocoagulation in wastewater treatment

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Abstract: The purpose of this study was to investigate the efficiency of electrocoagulation utilizing various configurations of aluminum and iron electrodes in eliminating chemical (chemical oxygen demand – COD, biochemical oxygen demand – BOD, total suspended solids – TSS, turbidity, total phosphorous) and microbiological characteristics from municipal wastewater. In addition, the obtained effluent was compared with the existing Regulation (EU) 2020/741 on minimum requirements for water reuse when it comes to the potential of its use as a resource in e.g. irrigation of agricultural land. Based on the research findings, one can conclude that the electrocoagulation technique could be used to efficiently remove chemical and microbiological pollutants from municipal wastewater. Multiple electrode configurations (experiment sets: E1-E8) were used throughout the study to find the most effective one. By observing the obtained results and the achieved removal efficiencies, it was concluded that the E8 treatment, in which the bipolar arrangement of electrodes (Al(-)/Al/Al/Al(+)) was applied, was the most effective, given that satisfactory efficiencies were achieved for all physico-chemical (COD= 74%, BOD=79%, TSS=98%, turbidity= 96%, total P= 100%) and microbiological parameters (total coliform, fecal coliforms, *E.coli*, fecal streptococci, *Salmonella sp.* ~ 100%) except for N (6%). Additional analyzes, such as electrical conductivity (1,27 mS/cm) and sodium adsorption ratio (SAR= 8,06) revealed that water purified in this way could be used for irrigation of soils with good permeability. Future work will optimize the process by selecting appropriate electrode combinations. Furthermore, the resultant precipitate will be investigated as a possible nutritional resource.

Keywords: wastewater treatment; electrocoagulation; nutrients; wastewater reuse

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